

Impact of double stratification on heat and mass transfer analysis of magnetic nanofluid flow over a stretching sheet

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Abstract

The study addresses the heat and mass transfer occurring over a stretched surface in both steady and unsteady states of nanofluid, factoring in magnetic field effects, thermal stratification, and solutal stratification. The governing partial differential equations for boundary layer flow, heat, and mass transfer are transformed into ordinary differential equations using the similarity variable technique. These equations are then numerically solved via the Galerkin Finite Element Method. A comprehensive parametric analysis is conducted, presenting numerical results for velocity, temperature, and concentration profiles, alongside the skin-friction parameter, Nusselt number, and Sherwood number, all illustrated through graphs and tables. It is observed that as the thermal stratification parameter (St) increases, the temperature profiles weaken. Similarly, an increase in the solutal stratification parameter (Sm) leads to a decline in concentration profiles.

Keywords: MHD nanofluid; Steady and unsteady stretching sheet; Thermal stratification; Solutal stratification; heat generation/absorption.

Nomenclature			
T_w	Temperature at the cone surface	(u,v)	Velocity components in x- and y-axis (m/s)
S_t	Thermal Stratification parameter	T	Fluid temperature (K)
q_w	Wall heat flux	S_m	Mass stratification parameter
Ra	Mixed convection parameter	q_r	Radiative heat flux
P	Pressure (Pa)	R	Radiation parameter
Nt	Thermophoresis parameter	Nu_x	Nusselt number
M	Magnetic parameter	Nr	Buoyancy ratio parameter
K^*	Mean absorption coefficient	<i>Greek symbols</i>	
$A1, B1$	Source/sink parameters	α	Thermal diffusivity of base fluid (m^2/s)
A	Constant	β	Thermal expansion coefficient ($1/K$)
B_0	Magnetic field strength	η	Similarity variable
B	Constants	ρ_f	Fluid density ($kg\ m^{-3}$)
C	Nanoparticle volume fraction	ψ	Stream function
C	Constant	τ	Parameter defined by $\varepsilon \frac{(\rho c)_p}{(\rho c)_f}$
C_f	Skin-friction coefficient	$(\rho c_p)_f$	Heat capacitance of the base fluid
c_p	Specific heat (J/kg K)	$(\rho c_p)_p$	Heat capacitance of the nanofluid
C_w	Nanoparticle volume fraction on the cone	ρ_p	Density of the nanofluid
C_∞	Ambient nanoparticle volume fraction	σ	Electrical conductivity
D	Constant	τ	Unsteadiness parameter
D_B	Brownian diffusion coefficient (m^2/s)	<i>Subscripts</i>	
D_T	Thermophoretic diffusion coefficient (m^2/s)	f	Base fluid
$f(\eta)$	Dimensionless stream function	w	Condition at cone surface
g	Gravitational acceleration vector (m/s^2)	∞	Condition far away from cone surface

1. Introduction

Recent advancements in nanotechnology offer both physical and chemical methods to create nanometer-sized particles or nanostructured materials engineered at the atomic or molecular level, resulting in enhanced thermo-physical properties compared to their bulk counterparts. Nanofluids are formed by dispersing nanometer-sized particles in base fluids such as water, oil, or ethylene glycol. These nanofluids can be prepared using nanoparticles from various materials, including metallic oxides (Al_2O_3 , CuO), nitride ceramics (AlN , SiN), carbide ceramics (SiC , TiC), metals (Cu , Ag , Au), semiconductors (TiO_2 , SiC), and single, double, or multi-walled carbon nanotubes. These nanofluids help improve thermal conductivity and enhance heat transfer performance even at low volume fractions of suspended particles.

Choi (1995) reported on the MHD boundary layer heat transfer characteristics of nanofluid flow over an exponentially stretching sheet influenced by chemical reactions. Eastmen et al. (2001) studied the thermal conductivity of ethylene glycol-based nanofluids containing copper nanoparticles, finding that the thermal conductivity of these nanofluids surpassed that of pure ethylene glycol with the same volume fraction of dispersed oxide nanoparticles. Buongiorno (2006) introduced seven slip mechanisms to enhance the thermal conductivity effect of nanoparticles, including Brownian diffusion, inertia, diffusiophoresis, thermophoresis, fluid drainage, Magnus effect, and gravity, concluding that thermophoresis and Brownian diffusion are the most significant slip mechanisms in nanofluids. Abu-Nada and Oztop (2009) examined the influence of inclination angle on natural convection heat transfer in a two-dimensional enclosure filled with Cu-water-based nanofluid, concluding that heat transfer enhancement slows with higher Rayleigh numbers. Kuznetsov and Nield (2010) presented an analytical solution for natural convective boundary layer flow of nanofluid through a vertical plate, finding that the Nusselt number decreases with lower values of thermophoresis and Brownian motion. Hammad (2011) studied the convective flow and heat transfer of an incompressible viscous nanofluid over a stretching sheet. Noghrehabadi et al. (2012) analyzed slip effects on boundary layer flow and heat transfer over a stretching surface, considering nanoparticle volume fraction. Rashidi et al. (2014) investigated the buoyancy effects on MHD boundary layer flow and heat transfer of nanofluid over a stretching sheet with thermal radiation. Zargartalebi et al. (2015) explored the influence of stagnation-point and nanoparticle volume fraction over an isothermal stretching sheet, examining the concentration distribution of nanoparticles in the boundary layer with zero flux at the sheet surface.

Khan et al. (2016) studied heat and mass transfer characteristics of nanofluid over a stretching sheet saturated with porous media and thermal radiation. Sudarsana Reddy and Chamkha (2016) examined MHD boundary layer flow, heat, and mass transfer characteristics of nanofluid saturated with porous media over a vertical cone, considering various aspects of nanoparticles such as type, shape, size, and base fluid in the presence of a drift-flux model. Makinde et al. (2016) investigated the heat and mass transfer flow of electrically conducting nanofluid over a radially stretching surface with thermophoresis and Brownian motion.

Sudarsan Reddy et al. (2017) studied the heat and mass transfer flow of Cu-water and Ag-water nanofluids with nanoparticle volume fractions ranging from 1% to 4% over a rotating disk saturated with porous media, considering partial slip and thermal radiation parameters.

All the aforementioned studies focus on steady flows. However, unsteadiness in fluid flow, heat, and mass transfer problems is a crucial aspect. Bachok et al. (2012) examined unsteady boundary layer flow of a nanofluid over a permeable shrinking/stretching sheet. Khalili et al. (2014) discussed stagnation point flow and heat transfer of unsteady nanofluid over a shrinking/stretching sheet with a magnetic field, concluding that the permeability parameter has a greater influence on heat transfer than the magnetic field parameter. Makinde and Tshehla (2014) explored the impact of Navier slip, viscous dissipation, ohmic heating, and Newtonian heating on unsteady MHD flow of nanofluids over a moving vertical plate, noting that the skin friction coefficient decreases with increasing slip and Newtonian heating parameters. Das et al. (2016) presented unsteady mixed convective flow over spherical and cylindrical bodies filled with nanofluid in the presence of a magnetic field. Pop et al. (2016) conducted a theoretical study on unsteady boundary layer heat transfer of nanofluid over a permeable curved shrinking/stretching surface with a magnetic field. Hayat et al. (2016) investigated the effect of stratification on unsteady flow of nanofluid over an inclined

stretching sheet, reporting that velocity distributions deteriorate with higher thermal and solutal stratification parameters. Ibrahim and Makinde (2013) reported bio-convective flow of nanofluid over a permeable vertical plate in a magnetic field due to gyrostatic microorganisms with double stratification. Khalil et al. (2016) examined mixed convection Eyring-Powell fluid flow over an inclined stretching cylinder in a double stratified medium. Kandaswamy et al. (2018) investigated thermal and solutal stratification flow, heat, and mass transfer of nanofluid saturated with porous medium over a vertical plate, concluding that temperature and concentration profiles diminish with increasing thermal and solutal stratification parameters. Farooq et al. (2017) presented MHD stagnation point flow and melting heat transfer of nanofluids over a nonlinear stretching surface with variable thickness. Yasin et al. (2013) discussed thermal stratification on steady mixed convection boundary layer flow of nanofluid saturated by a porous medium over a vertical surface. Hayat et al. (2016) presented the convective flow between coaxial rotating stretchable disks of nanofluid in a thermally stratified medium with a magnetic field, concluding that the temperature profile diminishes with increasing thermal stratification parameter. Rehman et al. (2017) discussed MHD boundary layer flow of Eyring-Powell nanofluid over an inclined stretching cylinder with thermal stratification, concluding that the skin-friction coefficient decreases with improving mixed convection parameter values. Daniel et al. (2017) examined unsteady mixed convection heat transfer flow of nanofluid over a permeable stretching sheet using the Buongiorno model in a magnetic field with thermal and solutal stratification, reporting that the Nusselt number decreases with higher Buoyancy ratio parameter values, while the Sherwood number increases with rising mixed convection parameter values. Ramzan et al. (2017) observed heat and mass transfer characteristics of micropolar nanofluid in a magnetic field with radiation and double stratification. Mutuku et al. (2017) studied unsteady MHD boundary layer heat and mass transfer flow of nanofluid over a flat surface

with double stratification, noticing that the temperature profile shrinks with higher thermal stratification parameter values. Mehmood et al. (2016) revealed the effects of thermal and solutal stratification on unsteady MHD boundary layer heat and mass transfer flow of viscous nanofluid over an inclined stretching sheet, reporting that the velocity profile diminishes with rising thermal and mass stratification parameters. Several authors (Prabhavathi et al., 2017, Rajaobula Reddy et al., 2017, Sreedevi et al., 2017a, Rawat et al., 2018, Gireesha et al., 2018, Pandey et al., 2018, Kandwal et al., 2019) have discussed the heat and mass transfer characteristics of Tiwari-Das and Buongiorno mathematical models of nanofluids over different geometries.

2. Mathematical Analysis

We study the two-dimensional, incompressible, unsteady nanofluid flow over a stretching sheet saturated by porous medium with the impact of thermal stratification, solutal stratification and non-uniform heat source/sink. The coordinate system is such that x -axis is taken along the stretching surface in the direction of the motion and y – axis is perpendicular to the surface of the sheet as shown schematically in Fig. 1. A uniform magnetic field B_0 is applied along the y – axis . The surface of the sheet is preserved at unchanging temperature $T_w = T_0 + \frac{Ax}{1-at}$ and concentration $C_w = C_0 + \frac{Dx}{1-at}$ and these values are expected to be greater than the ambient temperature stratified in the form $T_\infty = T_0 + \frac{Bx}{1-at}$ and concentration stratified in the form $C_\infty = C_0 + \frac{Ex}{1-at}$. Under the above conventions the governing equations represents the continuity, momentum, energy and concentration take the following form:

$$\phi'' - Sc (f \phi' - f' \phi) - Sc S_m f' - Sc \tau \left(S_m + \phi + \frac{1}{2} \eta \phi' \right) + \left(\frac{Nt}{Nb} \right) \theta'' = 0 \quad (10)$$

The boundary conditions take the form

$$f = 0, \quad f' = 1, \quad \theta = 1 - S_t, \quad \phi = 1 - S_m, \quad \text{at} \quad \eta = 0, \quad (11)$$

$$f' \rightarrow 0, \quad \theta \rightarrow 0, \quad \phi \rightarrow 0, \quad \text{at} \quad \eta \rightarrow \infty. \quad (12)$$

where superscript signifies differentiation with respect to η .

The pertinent parameters uttering the flow dynamics are demarcated by

$$Nr = \frac{(\rho^* - \rho)(C_w - C_0)}{\rho \beta_T (T_w - T_0)(1 - C_\infty)}, \quad Pr = \frac{\nu}{\alpha}, \quad M = \frac{\sigma \beta_0^2}{\rho b}, \quad S_t = \frac{B}{A}, \quad S_m = \frac{E}{D},$$

$$Sc = \frac{\nu}{D_B}, \quad \tau = \frac{a}{b}, \quad Ra = \frac{(1 - C_\infty) g \beta_T (T_w - T_0)}{b^2 x}, \quad Nb = \frac{\tau D_B (C_w - C_0)}{\nu}, \quad Nt = \frac{\tau D_T (T_w - T_0)}{\nu T_\infty},$$

Quantities of practical interest in this problem are skin-friction coefficient (C_f), local Nusselt number (Nu_x), and the local Sherwood number (Sh_x), which are defined as

$$C_f = \frac{\tau_w}{\rho U^2}, \quad Nu_x = \frac{x q_w}{k(T_w - T_\infty)}, \quad Sh_x = \frac{x J_w}{D_B (C_w - C_\infty)} \quad (13)$$

Where the surface shear stress τ_w , wall heat flux q_w and wall mass flux J_w are given by

$$\tau_w = \mu \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)_{y=0}, \quad q_w = - \left(k + \frac{16 T_\infty^3 \sigma^*}{3 K^*} \right) \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right)_{y=0}, \quad J_w = - D_B \left(\frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \right)_{y=0} \quad (14)$$

By using above equations we get

$$C_f (Re_x)^{1/2} = f''(0), \quad Nu_x (Re_x)^{-1/2} = -(1 + R) \left(\frac{1}{1 - S_t} \right) \theta'(0),$$

$$Sh_x (Re_x)^{-1/2} = - \left(\frac{1}{1 - S_m} \right) \phi'(0).$$

Where $Re_x = \frac{Ux}{\nu}$ is the local Reynolds number.

3. Numerical method of solution:

The finite element method (FEM) is such a powerful method for solving ordinary differential equations and partial differential equations. The basic idea of this method is dividing the whole domain into smaller elements of finite dimensions called finite elements. This method is such a good numerical method in modern engineering analysis, and it can be

applied for solving integral equations including heat transfer, fluid mechanics, chemical processing, electrical systems, and many other fields. The steps involved in the finite element method “(Sreedevi et al., 2017b, Sudarsana Reddy et al. 2016a, Sudarsana Reddy et al. 2016b)” are as follows.

- (i) *Finite-element discretization*
- (ii) *Generation of the element equations*
- (iii) *Assembly of element equations*
- (iv) *Imposition of boundary conditions*
- (v) *Solution of assembled equations*

4. Results and discussion

In this section, we present a thorough numerical analysis of relevant parameters affecting the velocity, temperature, and concentration profiles in both steady and unsteady cases of nanofluid. The results are depicted graphically in Figures 2 to 18. The impact of various parameters on the hydrodynamic, thermal, and solutal boundary layers is examined, and the findings are compared with those of Sreedevi et al. [40], as shown in Table 1.

The influence of the magnetic parameter (M) on velocity, temperature, and concentration distributions for both steady and unsteady cases is depicted in Figures 2-4. It is observed that the velocity profiles decrease with increasing values of (M), with a more significant reduction in the unsteady case. This is due to the Lorentz force generated in the electrically conducting fluid when a magnetic field is present, which opposes the flow direction and reduces velocity. Conversely, the thermal and solutal boundary layer thicknesses increase with higher (M) values, more so in the steady state than in the unsteady state.

Figures 5 and 6 illustrate the effect of the mixed convection parameter (Ra) on velocity and temperature distributions in both steady and unsteady nanofluids. Velocity profiles increase with higher (Ra) values across the boundary layer, with a more pronounced effect in the steady case. However, temperature distributions decrease as (Ra) values increase.

The impact of the Buoyancy ratio parameter (Nr) on velocity and temperature profiles is shown in Figures 7-8. Velocity increases significantly with higher (Nr) values, more so in the steady case (Figure 7). Meanwhile, temperature profiles decrease with increasing (Nr) values, with a greater reduction observed in the unsteady case (Figure 8).

Figures 9-10 reveal the effect of the Prandtl number (Pr) on velocity and temperature profiles for both cases. Both velocity and temperature profiles decrease with higher (Pr) values in both steady and unsteady states. Figure 11 summarizes the variations in temperature profiles for different values of the thermal stratification parameter (St). It is found that temperature profiles decrease throughout the boundary layer with increasing (St) values, with a greater reduction in the unsteady case compared to the steady case.

Figures 12-14 illustrate the effect of the Brownian motion number (Nb) on velocity, temperature, and concentration profiles for both cases. Velocity profiles decrease within the boundary layer with higher (Nb) values, more so in the unsteady case. However, both temperature and concentration profiles increase with higher (Nb) values in both steady and unsteady states, with a more significant enhancement in the steady case.

Figures 15-17 show the effect of the thermophoretic parameter (Nt) on velocity, temperature, and concentration profiles. Both velocity and temperature profiles increase with higher (Nt) values, with a slightly greater increase in the steady case. However, concentration profiles decrease with higher (Nt) values. Additionally, Figure 18 shows that concentration

profiles compress throughout the boundary layer with higher values of the mass stratification parameter (S_m), with a more significant compression in the unsteady case compared to the steady case.

Table 2 characterizes the values of the skin-friction coefficient ($-f'(0)$), Nusselt number ($-\theta'(0)$), and Sherwood number ($-\phi'(0)$) for various parameter values in both steady and unsteady cases. It is reported that velocity increases while heat and mass transfer rates decrease in both steady and unsteady nanofluids with higher (M) values. The skin-friction coefficient, Nusselt number, and Sherwood number decrease with higher (N_b) values. The non-dimensional velocity and mass transfer rates increase, while heat transfer rates decrease with higher (N_t) values in both steady and unsteady cases. The skin-friction coefficient increases, while Nusselt and Sherwood numbers decrease with higher (S_t) values in both steady and unsteady nanofluids. Additionally, the skin-friction coefficient and Nusselt number increase with higher (S_m) values, whereas the Sherwood number decreases in both steady and unsteady cases.

5. Conclusion

In this analysis, we have examined the boundary layer flow, heat, and mass transfer of steady and unsteady nanofluid flow over a stretching surface saturated by a porous medium, considering the effects of magnetic field, thermal stratification, and mass stratification. The resulting nonlinear ordinary differential equations were solved using the Finite Element Method. The significant conclusions drawn from the graphical and numerical solutions are as follows:

- i) Heat transfer rate increases in both steady and unsteady cases as the values of the mass stratification parameter (S_m) rise.

- ii) Both heat and mass transfer rates decrease in both cases as the values of the thermal stratification parameter (St) rise.
- iii) The velocity and temperature of the fluid increase, while concentration profiles deteriorate with increasing values of the thermophoretic parameter (Nt).
- iv) Higher values of the buoyancy ratio parameter (Nr) enhance the velocity profiles in both cases, while the temperature profiles decrease in both steady and unsteady cases.

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Fig. 6. Effect of (**Ra**) on Temperature profiles.

Fig. 7. Effect of (**Nr**) on velocity profiles.

Fig. 8. Effect of (**Nr**) on temperature profiles.

Fig. 9. Effect of (**Pr**) on velocity profiles.

Fig. 10. Effect of (**Pr**) on temperature profiles.

Fig. 11. Effect of (**St**) on Temperature profiles.

Fig. 12. Effect of (**Nb**) on velocity profiles.

Fig. 13. Effect of (**Nb**) on temperature profiles

Fig. 14. Effect of (**Nb**) on concentration profiles.

Fig. 15. Effect of (**Nt**) on velocity profiles.

Fig. 16. Effect of (**Nt**) on Temperature profiles.

Fig. 17. Effect of (**Nt**) on Concentration profiles.

Table 1: Comparison of $(-\theta'(0))$ with available work for $M = 0.1, Nr = 0.5, R = 0.1,$
 $Cr = 0.1, A1 = 0, B1 = 0, Pr = 1.0, Ra = 0.5, Le = 1.0.$

Parameter		$-\theta'(0)$			
		Sreedevi et al. (2017b)		Present Study	
Nb	Nt	steady	unsteady	steady	unsteady
1.0	1.0	0.23636	0.22910	0.23640	0.22914
1.5	1.0	0.17894	0.17326	0.17898	0.17330
2.0	1.0	0.13293	0.12859	0.13295	0.12863
2.5	1.0	0.09728	0.09402	0.09731	0.09406
1.0	0.1	0.31318	0.30379	0.31322	0.30382
1.0	0.3	0.29360	0.28476	0.29366	0.28479
1.0	0.5	0.27556	0.26721	0.27561	0.26725
1.0	0.7	0.25389	0.25104	0.25392	0.25108

Table 2: The sway of diverse parameters entered into the problem on skin – friction coefficient ($-f''(0)$), local Nusselt number ($-\theta'(0)$) and local Sherwood number ($-\phi'(0)$).

Parameters					$-f''(0)$		$-\theta'(0)$		$-\phi'(0)$	
M	Nb	Nt	St	Sm	steady	unsteady	steady	unsteady	steady	unsteady
0.1	1.0	1.0	0.1	0.1	1.08033	1.21590	0.58650	0.68052	0.62885	0.79240
0.4	1.0	1.0	0.1	0.1	1.19837	1.32430	0.57277	0.67139	0.60192	0.77493
0.7	1.0	1.0	0.1	0.1	1.34696	1.46205	0.55597	0.66033	0.56986	0.75430
0.5	1.0	1.0	0.1	0.1	1.27860	1.39807	0.58211	0.69016	0.69415	0.87342
0.5	1.0	1.0	0.1	0.1	1.27583	1.39579	0.56934	0.67300	0.62083	0.79962
0.5	1.0	1.0	0.1	0.1	1.27321	1.39364	0.55952	0.65910	0.55003	0.72940
0.5	0.3	1.0	0.1	0.1	1.27333	1.39365	0.53044	0.62551	0.61291	0.79539
0.5	0.5	1.0	0.1	0.1	1.27415	1.39422	0.50123	0.59293	0.69820	0.88226
0.5	0.7	1.0	0.1	0.1	1.27428	1.39426	0.48514	0.57482	0.73448	0.91896
0.5	1.0	1.0	0.1	0.1	1.26076	1.38123	0.57595	0.66101	0.51660	0.70315
0.5	1.0	1.3	0.1	0.1	1.26200	1.38254	0.57370	0.66016	0.51640	0.70225
0.5	1.0	1.5	0.1	0.1	1.26449	1.38506	0.56923	0.65845	0.51602	0.70046
0.5	1.0	1.0	0.1	0.1	1.24822	1.36897	0.67519	0.80178	0.39100	0.46310
0.5	1.0	1.0	0.3	0.1	1.25478	1.37519	0.67921	0.80462	0.41583	0.48089
0.5	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.1	1.26793	1.38764	0.68730	0.81031	0.46556	0.51647